

Title: Redefining Human Nature in a Technology world

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INTRODUCTION:

Humans and Technology are on converging paths. Robotics can enhance humans, allowing disabled people to operate normally, and regular humans to gain "super powers". On the other end of the spectrum AI & Deep Learning are making machines more "human" while AR & VR can create immersive experiences that can feel real. How are these technologies challenging our definition of humanity and what it means to be human?

AIM:

Challenge the traditional thinking about what is "human" and demonstrate the boundaries stretched by emerging technologies

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

News, Articles and Product Briefs related to latest developments in Robotics, AI, AR/VR, and Digital Convergence. Results from experiments related to immersive experiences.

RESULTS:

N/A (this talk poses questions, does not provide answers)

CONCLUSIONS:

Humans and Technology are overlapping at an ever-increasing pace. We are consuming technology faster than our conscious awareness can absorb the implications. We are entering an era where conversations around humanity will take center stage.

KEYWORDS:

Humanity, Robotics, AI, Deep Learning, AR, VR

BIOGRAPHY:

Christos Kritikos is a San Francisco-based technologist & dreamer working as a full-lifecycle Product & Project Manager. He has participated in several companies, consulted for dozens of clients, ran numerous tech projects and managed digital & physical products. He is fascinated by technology's promise and apprehensive of her risks; still, he sees her as means to enhance our experience in the physical world and ultimately our life. **(Up to 100 words)**